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CLASSROOM ASSESSMENTS IN WRITING CLASSES

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Abstract. This article illustrates classroom assessment methods that are used to help teachers guide their students in writing classes and assist students in improving and monitor their learning. The author gives explanation to each classroom assessment which teachers can adopt or adapt to their students' learning styles and teaching milieu. In addition, samples of some classroom assessment methods are proposed that can be utilized in writing classes.

Key words: classroom assessment, portfolio, checklist, rubric, feedback, writing, technology

Assessment is deemed to be commonly discussed topic in language teaching classes due to its variety of uses, functions, purposes, and types. It has been perceived differently among teachers with negative and positive associations. It is understood by many as being a test which is wrong because test or testing is an assessment technique used to collect information about students' weaknesses and strengths. The information is used to make modifications to teaching materials and learning objectives. Many scholars point out that assessment is broad and it encompasses many ideas related to students, teachers and classroom itself. Ling He

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(2021), for example, in her article titled “Classroom Assessment for Academic Writing” discusses about classroom assessment. As the author states, classroom assessment has seen many changes in assessment of students’ writing. She mentions two key assessment types: assessment of learning and assessment for learning. Modern classes where academic writing is taught, have adopted assessment for learning method so as to aid students to improve their writing performance. According to Ling He, classroom assessment

- ❖ is present in the classroom with complex and shifting situations
- ❖ collaborates with activities that align with curriculum, learning objectives and classroom management
- ❖ encourages more active student participation and teachers’ modification to their materials in order to meet students’ needs
- ❖ helps teachers evaluate if students’ work aligns with learning objectives

During assessment for learning, students get a chance to improve their writing because all the activities done during classroom assessment is aimed to guide learners rather than to grade. Ling He suggests six forms of constructive feedback that can be utilized to motivate, encourage students to be more active learners:

written in-text comments: these are comments given in students’ essay. They can be eliciting questions or some specific recommendations

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Draft One: Literature review (standards, perceptions, stakeholders)

Please explain what you are going to do.

You will need to guide the reader from general to specific: What are standards, different types of standards; different language learning standards [CEFR, CSE, etc.]; AND FINALLY... WHY IT IS NECESSARY FOR US TO FOCUS ON THE ACTFL and adopt it for our own. THIS IS WHERE YOU ARE GOING TO LEAD THE READER.

~~Standards: _The literature on standards has highlighted several definitions. For example, according to Rose (2009) standards are criteria which aim at judging competence, and we are dependent on them regularly in variety aspects of life. This include sports, cooking, bringing children up, schooling, etc. Rose also mentions about the arguing feature of standards (p. 93), which means people tend to argue about them. Likewise,~~

question/answer: teachers and students interact with some questions and answers.

This can be done in multiple modes such as online or face to face in the classroom

individual conferencing: a teacher meets a student who is taking a writing course once a semester or often times with those who need more instructions

technology assisted feedback: a teacher works with student through technology such as Zoom, Telegram, VoiceThread, Panopto videos or Moodle to provide more, in-depth comments on students' work

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self-assessment: students are given some guidelines like Yes/no questions, a poll, a survey to help them reflect on their own writing

peer assessment: in this mode, students are involved in peer evaluation of their friends work and vice versa. Often times they are provided with checklists, rubrics so that they know on what to target their attention while reading peer work

portfolio: students can keep digital or physical form of portfolio. During the pandemic, when the whole world is suffering from COVID 19 outbreak, portfolio assessment is quite convenient and portable. Students can keep their works such as essays, multiple drafts, homework, feedback received from peers and teacher. Teachers may easily grade their students from students' performance in the portfolio.

Other methods that are used in my classroom include:

group work assessment: the whole class is grouped into two or three and are given an essay per person of the group. Each person should read the essay at home and come to lesson with some comments to the writer. Then, in the classroom students

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discuss what they have found as necessary. Teacher is only monitoring and enters into conversation where there is much argument.

docs.google.com assessment: this is a more innovative way of giving, receiving feedback and at the same time, teachers can involve the whole class to write an essay online right in the classroom or edit it. This technology-based learning or teaching really encourages students to be active learners.

analytic rubrics: They guide both students and teachers because they contain detailed explanation of course objectives and teacher expectations. They look like tables that contain assessment criteria which align with course goals (Becker, 2018).

Holistic Rubric

3	Layout is used correctly; punctuation, grammar, spelling and vocabulary are used properly; language is formal.
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2	Layout is generally used correctly; punctuation, grammar, spelling and vocabulary are mostly used correctly; language is virtually all formal.
1	Layout is generally used correctly; punctuation, grammar, spelling and vocabulary are mostly used accurately; language is virtually all formal.
0	No response

Checklists: Teachers can apply checklists to assess their students' weaknesses for performance tasks like writing and speaking. This tool assists students to succeed in producing a written work based on exact criteria. Teachers can use it to include necessary skills their students need to acquire in a particular writing class. (Akhmadjonov, 2018)

Sample checklist

Presenter Name:		Reviewer Name:	
Writing skill	Does the writer do this?		Write some notes about what the author did well, or ideas about how the writer could improve his/her skills.
	Yes	No	
Write clearly			

The above-mentioned methods definitely guide students and teachers to cope with their writing issues.

In conclusion, understanding assessment and proper application can lead to active learning among students. For teachers, it is necessary to use appropriate classroom assessment methods to make their job much easier and effective.

References

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